

Bid Analysis And End Price Prediction Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— One of the online ecommerce transactional methods with the quickest growth is online bidding.

The technology will analyse historical auction data and forecast the winning bid for upcoming auctions using machine learning algorithms. The prediction will be based on various factors such as the item description, bidding history, and final price of past auctions, as well as the current market conditions and bidding behavior of individual bidders. The system will provide valuable insights to sellers and bidders by predicting the end price of an auction, enabling them to make informed decisions. The prediction system will be trained and evaluated on a large dataset of historical auction data to ensure its accuracy and reliability. By introducing more open and effective pricing systems, the project's findings could have a substantial impact on the online auction sector.

Keywords— End price prediction, Machine learning, Linear Regression.

I. INTRODUCTION

Online auctions have emerged as one of the most significant web services, enabling users to sell and buy a variety of goods. Since bidders and sellers can greatly benefit from using the abovepredicted values, predicting the end price of an auction before it ends has become a topic of research that is becoming more and more relevant. Due to the great level of accuracy with which machine learning algorithms can anticipate test data, their potential is limitless. Various methods for end price prediction have been presented in the context of online auctions. These methods used time series analysis, functional data analysis, and machine learning to tackle the forecasting challenge. Online auctions not only minimize the work but also significantly contribute to skyrocketing profit graphs. Online auctions provide a lot of data that can be used for market research, product development, and services for buyers and sellers.

Machine learning techniques are applied to the obtained data for additional processing in order to forecast the auction item's final bid price. In order to maximize their personal revenues, buyers and sellers benefit from improving their understanding of and ability to predict the results of online auctions.

The inherent value of an item is reflected in the auction's ultimate sale pricing, which results in price variation that can be explained by elements like the item's start price, start date, end price, etc.

The proposed system's major objective is to increase accuracy. To determine whether the item will sell or not, the suggested method employs naive Bayes. The linear regression technique predicts the price at which an item will sell and whether or not it will maximize profit.

Regression because they generate a continuous value rather than a classified value as an output, algorithms like linear regression are used. As a result, it will be possible to ascertain a product's genuine value rather than just guessing its price range. Flask is used to develop a user interface that requests input from the user and presents the products' pricing based on that information.

A. Some Key facts

- The Product name, Category name, Starting date, Ending date, Start price, and End price are all some attributes which can influence the value of the product.
- The characteristics that affect the product's pricing may differ by region and are difficult to predict precisely.

B. Machine Learning

Computer science's field of machine learning enables machines to comprehend without being explicitly instructed. Machine learning is one of the most fascinating areas of technology ever. It gives the computer the ability to learn, as the name suggests, enhancing its sentience. Contrary to popular assumption, machine learning has a lot more uses right now.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

How to forecast the final price of the products has been the subject of numerous studies.

Machine learning Approach to forecast the final price of an online auction was created by Manali Rajendra Khadge and Milind V. Kulkarni. The proposed system's major objective is to increase accuracy. To determine whether the item will sell or not, the suggested method employs naive Bayes. The support vector machine algorithm determines whether or not the item will maximise profit by estimating the pricing. Xiaohui Li, Shuang Han, and Hongbin Dong* constructed "Multiple Linear Regression with Kalman Filter for Predicting End Prices of Online Auctions". This study proposes a hybrid method (MLRKF) that combines multiple linear regression and Kalman filter to improve end price prediction accuracy while requiring less training data. When using the multiple linear regression approach to predict in machine learning, the difficulties of low prediction accuracy and over fitting are addressed by the suggested technique. First, Kalman filter and multiple linear regression models are described and examined. Second, we conceptualise the multiple linear regression prediction problem as a weight parameter optimisation problem and theoretically show the strategy. After that, an MLRKF prediction model is offered. On the basis of two datasets, the suggested model is then utilised to forecast eBay final prices.

Sandeep Kumar evaluated several pricing structures. Sandeep Kumar chose the auction price using the clustering method. His approach divides the input auctions into groups of comparable auctions based on their numerous qualities using the k-means algorithm. The k-means technique, which employs one way analysis of variance, uses the elbow approach to determine the value of k. Several pricing algorithms, including time series and decision tree price estimation, are compared to this strategy. . The feasibility of applying data mining techniques to price determination in a unique strategy for forecasting online auction prices is examined. Decision trees are used to verify several auctions.

Using naive Bayes, David Nicholson and Rohan Paranjpe's technique forecasts whether an item will sell or not at auction. using the eBay Application Programming Interface to access the data. The ultimate bid price of the eBay auction is predicted using uniform prior naive bayes. The only factor considered in determining the final price is the item title. The prediction accuracy of Naive Bayes for whether a product would sell or not was over 75%. The results showed that the uniform prior naive bayes model over predicts, which causes misclassification.

III. METHODOLOGY

The system has two fundamental phases:

1. Training phase: Using an appropriate algorithm selected based on values from the data set, the system is taught to fit the model (line/curve).
2. The system is pushed through its paces and put through numerous tests during the testing stage to see if it is

effective and functional. The accuracy has been verified twice. It must be appropriate in order to test or simulate it.

A. Pycharm

PyCharm is a dedicated Python Integrated Development Environment (IDE) that includes a variety of critical utilities for Python programmers and developers that are tightly integrated to provide a comfortable workspace for effective Python, data science and web development. *B. Pycharm Features:*

PyCharm offers code inspections, smart code completion, on-the-fly mistake flagging and quick fixes, as well as rich navigation and automated code refactorings. □ Intelligent Code Editor: PyCharm's smart code editor provides the best support for Python, CSS, JavaScript, TypeScript, CoffeeScript, famous template languages and more.

- Smart Code Navigation: PyCharm's clever smart search can be used to quickly navigate to any class, folder, or symbol, as well as any IDE action or tool window.
- Fast and Safe Refactorings: With safe Rename and Delete, Extract Method, Inline Variable or Method, Introduce Variable, and more code refactoring, you may refactor your code intelligently.
- Debugging, Profiling and Testing: For Python and JavaScript, users can utilize the sophisticated debugger with an excellent graphical user interface. □ Database tools: MySQL, SQL Server, PostgreSQL, Oracle, and other databases can be accessed directly from the IDE.

B. Flask

Flask is a simple and lightweight Python web framework that offers the necessary capabilities and resources for creating cutting-edge Python applications. You may easily create a web application using just one Python file, giving developers greater choice and making it an alluring framework for new developers.

Flask promises capabilities like interoperability with Google App Engine, integrated support for unit testing, and development server and debugger.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

We are using the Linear Regression method to build or improve a suitable and effective model for forecasting the cost of products based on the data we have available.

1) Data Collection:

We'll examine a data collection that contains details about products from the Kaggle repository. An end price can be anticipated based on a variety of variables. The Kaggle data set includes significant variables that

affect the used products's value or price. This data has been meticulously cleansed.

Table 1: Attributes and its Values

Input Attributes	Function/Values
Prod_name	Name of the product
Cat_name	Name of the category
Start_date	Starting date
End_date	Ending date
Starting_price	Starting price
Ending_price	Ending price

1) Algorithm:

One of the most fundamental and widely applied Machine Learning techniques is the linear regression algorithm. It is a method for using statistics to undertake predictive analysis.

"Linear regression" or "linear analysis" is the process of determining a linear connection between a dependent variable (y) and one or more independent variables (x). It may be possible to understand how the value of the dependent variable changes in response to changes in the value of the independent variable using linear regression, which shows a linear relationship.

Fig 1: Representation of linear regression

According to Fig. 1, linear regression can be expressed as

$$y = a_0 + a_1x +$$

Here, y is the dependent variable (the target variable)

x is the independent variable (the predictor variable).

ϵ = random error,

a_1 = Linear regression coefficient,

a_0 = line intercept.

The training datasets for a linear regression model representation are the x and y parameter values.

Fig2 : flask user interface

Fig3: Prediction is given according to the user inputs

V. CONCLUSION

Machine learning-based end price prediction is a promising area with numerous potential applications. Machine learning algorithms can evaluate large data sets to uncover patterns and trends that can be used to precisely anticipate future pricing.

This proposed model can be of great help for the sellers. With the help of this proposed model to predict the closing prices accurately.

REFERENCES

- [1] Manali Rajendra Khadge, Milind V Kulkarni "Machine Learning Approach For Predicting End Price Of Online Auction", Issue Pune 2016
- [2] Xiaohui Li, Shuang Han, Hongbin Dong* "Multiple Linear Regression with Kalman Filter for Predicting End Prices of Online Auctions", Harbin 2020
- [3] Sandeep kumar, "Pricing Algorithms In Online Auctions", International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering, Volume 3, Issue 6, June 2013
- [4] David Nicholson, Rohan Paranjpe "A Novel Method for Predicting the End-Price of eBay Auctions"stanford,2013